

PRODUCT PACKAGING AND PROFITABILITY OF SELECTED SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN ENUGU STATE

¹Obasi, Ikechi Agwu and ²Omife, Darlington Chidera

¹Department of Library UNN University of Nsukka, Enugu Campus

²Department of Marketing Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Email: ikechi.obasi@unn.edu.ng / omeifederam@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15441428>

Abstract: The study examined the influence of product packaging on profitability of bakery firms in Enugu State. Survey research design was used for this study. Data for the study were obtained through questionnaire administered to 350 respondents across the three senatorial districts in Enugu State. A purposive sampling was used to select the respondents for this study. A total of 322 copies of questionnaire were retrieved and used for the analysis. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Data obtained for the study were analyzed using tables, frequency and percentage while hypotheses were tested using multiple linear regression. The findings revealed that there was significant positive relationship between design of wrapper and printed information on profitability of small and medium bakery firms in Enugu State. This implies that when there is an improvement in design of wrapper and printed information on bakery products there will be significant positive influence on the profitability of the bakery firms. It concluded that packaging plays an important role in marketing and could be treated as one of the vital components of product that influence profitability. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that attention should be given to the overall improvement of design of wrapper and printed information by bakery firms in offering their products to the target market.

Keywords: Product Packaging, Profitability, Bakery Firms, Wrapper Design, Printed Information

Introduction

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have been recognized as main sustenance of the national development because of their capacity in enhancing the economic output and human welfare (Akingunola, 2011). SMEs experience difficulties in absorbing and coping with obstacles, they need to develop an ability to deal with the ever-increasing challenges in the global market (Dzisi & Ofosu, 2014). Moreso small and medium enterprises drive development as they create employment and contribute to the gross domestic product (GDP) (Kuteyi, 2013). The sector is a nursery of entrepreneurship, often driven by individual creativity and innovation (Ayozie & Latinwo, 2010).

In current competitive market, product packaging is a critical component that can influence the buying behaviour of customers and profitability of firms in the market. This is because product packaging can help differentiate similar products and provide a competitive advantage for firms to attract more potential customers to purchase their products (Klimchuk & Krasovec, 2007).

Based on packaging research by Hussain et al. (2015), the colour of the package is vital since it identifies the product from others in the firm. The more colourful the packaging, the more interested people are in products. In a highly competitive environment, companies use a variety of packing colours to attract customers and remind them of their products. Besides, packaging material is also important since it prevents losses; if enough material is used, people will be more attracted to the products. The proper brand-related image for a product's packaging can aid to grab customers' attention and affect their buying intent (Hussain *et al.*, 2015). Whereas, graphic design involves the name, type, and structure design, which includes packaging or product size (Nilsson & Ostrom, 2014).

Moreover, when consumers cannot determine the quality of a product simply on the appearance of the packaging, the size and shape of the packaging will have a significant influence on their purchase intent and profitability of the firms (Silayoi & Speece, 2007). Product packaging with larger size and shape will provide superior value than the product packaging in small size and shape in terms of customer purchase intention (Vila, 2006).

Nowadays, packaging is used by small and medium enterprise as a sales and marketing technique. Customer purchase behaviour is mainly influenced by packaging elements such as package quality, colour, wrapping, and others. Packaging is a complete solution that acts as the last selling point and promotes impulsive buying. Packaging increases revenue and market share while reducing marketing and advertising costs. Asserts that a package piques a consumer's interest in a certain brand, develops its reputation, and enhances how the products are perceived by the customers (Rundh, 2005). Additionally, packaging supports buyer in choosing an item from a board range of options and provides value to items (Underwood et al., 2001; Silayoi, & Speece, 2007). Packaging is also vital in the marketing environment where the best packaging creates a positive impression of the product in the mind of the consumer (AliceLouw, 2006).

In today's economy, there are many small and medium enterprises that offer the same goods in the economy of today. Consumers are exposed to thousands of brands in just one trip to the store. Therefore, in today's aggressive market, packaging has developed into a significant tools and marketing strategy for capturing customers' buying intention and enhancing profitability (Ranjbarian et al., 2012). Packaging can help differentiate a product or provide it a competitive advantage (Klimchuk & Krasovec, 2007). Nilsson and Ostrom (2014) graphic design which involve the name, printing labels, and structure layout, which includes packaging or product size. All aspects of packaging have a beneficial impact on the consumer's brand experience and purchase choice, resulting in brand loyalty (Sukri et al., 2014).

Small and medium enterprises may utilize packaging to encourage consumers and get a competitive edge over their competition. The colour of the package is crucial since it distinguishes the product from others in the firm. The more colourful the packaging, the more interested people are in the items. In a competitive market, small and medium enterprises utilised a variety of packing colours to attract customers and remind them of their products. Packaging material is also significant since it prevents losses; if enough material is utilised, people will be attracted to products. Font style is printed on packaging based on customer perception, since firms who employ the best font style effectively grab market share.

A successful marketing strategy by SME'S usually depends on a firm's understanding of its customers, what they need and how it persuades them to buy from it. This helps the firms to have a focus and also the bearing to attain its destination which enables the company to achieve its marketing objectives (Jain, 1990). Onah and Thomas (2004) postulate that marketing strategy must be specified in terms of product strategy, pricing strategy, promotional strategy and distribution strategy. Onah and Thomas (2004) see product strategy as containment and packing prior to sale with the primary purpose of facilitating the purchase and use of a product; hence the basic functions of packaging include: protection, utility function, motivation, profitability, and product differentiation.

It is against this background that the study intends examining the influence of product packaging on profitability of small and medium scale bakery firms in Enugu State. The study would focus on two distinct packaging characteristics: design of wrappers and Printed information and its respective influence on profitability of SME's.

Statement of Problem

Most small and medium enterprises which comprise bakery firms in both developing and developed countries face a lot of challenges in their bid to remain afloat and continue to satisfy the demands of customers. The situation is very worrisome especially in developing countries like Nigeria where sales volume and profits of most bakery firms have nose-dived to dangerous levels and many have closed down as a result. The question arises how the big bakery firms like UAC of Nigeria Plc bakers of the nationally popular Gala brand, Yale Foods limited (bakers of Yale bread), Leventis Foods, Shoprite, Spar, Roban, Celebrities etc. are succeeding in the face of such claimed harsh economic environmental factors. Thus, most academics argue that the faulty combination of the marketing mix variables by the small and medium-scale bakeries in Nigeria (Enugu inclusive) is behind the dwindling demands in their products, which manifest in dwindling profits and final liquidation of many. In other words, bakery firms' incapability of hiring astute sales professionals who could be of immense help in developing appropriate product strategies portend a dire challenge that might lead to lower sales volume in the industry as there are various assortments of bread with different packaging labels in Enugu State. It remains to be seen how product packaging does influence these bakeries in terms of profitability. It is against the backdrop that the study intends therefore to examine the influence of product packaging on profitability of small and medium scale bakery Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of Product Packaging on Profitability of Small and Medium Bakery Firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the effect of design of wrapper on the profitability of small and medium bakery firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Examine the degree to which printed information affect profitability of small and medium bakery firms in Enugu State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Product Packaging

Kotler and Armstrong (2016), packaging is the process of designing and producing the container or wrapper for a product. Agariya, Johari, Sharma, Chandraul and Singh (2012) described packaging as a container for a product including the physical appearance of the container such as the design, colour, shape, labeling and material.

Design

Dunmade (2015), the design of the product's wrapper has a long way to attract or distract product's consumers. The author stated that consumers are more sensitive to attributes or features that constitute design of wrapper, since consumers especially children are always attracted to the product design. Ahmadi, Bahrami and Ahani (2013) opined that the design of wrapper would normally provide attraction leading to the consumer's buying a product. Therefore, producers often try their best to develop a wrapper or container that has attractive influence on consumer to gain a competitive advantage over others companies.

Printed Information

Printed information gives the consumer first line information about a product and it is essential in attracting consumer attention to the product. It informs the consumer about the nature of the product and helps the consumers to take a decision (Borishade et al 2015). According to White (2015), printed information is essential because it conveys important information like marketing messages with the materials or ingredients used to produce the product. White (2015) asserted that the printed information on packaging creates brand identity and enhances recognition of product name. Deliya and Parmar (2017) stated that the printed information on packages is an essential element of marketing mix and can support advertising claims as well as enhance name recognition, establish brand identity and can optimally allocate shelf space.

Packaging Graphic

Lynsey (2023) opined that graphic images on a package can establish interest and also increase consumer curiosity for a specific product. The author established that packaging image is different and it has the capacity to establish interest for that product. Smith and Taylor (2013) opined that graphics can communicate on diverse levels, meaning that it can also create uniqueness to reinforce a brand image or name, help in shelf appearance and reposition.

Profitability

Profit is one of the core objectives of any firm for its long-term reputation and survival. Profitability is the profit-making ability which is considered an important factor for perpetual existence of firms. Measuring firm's profitability or taking into effect how well a business is being run is a very difficult task. There are various approaches that have been developed. It can be measuring the process of gain sharing financially or in economic terms, depending on the prevailing situation and the current scenario. As we know that there is a strong bonding between the profitability and the growth. Profitability is also cause of maximizes the values of stakeholders as well as investors and also show the performance of any firm in competent environment.

Sales Turnover

Sales turnover refers to how often a company sells its entire inventory to target customers. It may be described as the total amount of goods a company sells within a specific period of time, usually on yearly basis. Sales turnover refers to how often a company sells its inventory (Kennan, 2015). Different time- frames can be used

to measure the sales turnover of a company. Organisations chooses their time-frame to measure sales turnover. For instance, some companies may decide to measure their sales turnover weekly or monthly while others yearly (Pendharkar & Pandey, 2011). In accounting, sales turnover of a company is usually measured yearly. A firm's competitiveness impacts on profits via sales turnover rate. Sales turnover rate is therefore a significant indicator of market performance, particularly sales performance of a firm (Sajuyigbe, et al, 2013).

Repeat Purchase

This is the desire of a customer to patronize a product brand or company service repeatedly. In other words, repeat purchase is the willingness of a customer to make repeat purchase from a particular firm. Servais & Jensen (2012) defined repeat purchase as a behaviour whereby a customer patronizes a company's product or services repeatedly. In marketing the quest for repeat purchase is very high. It will bring a number of benefits to the customers such as, personal recognition, preferential treatment, discount, credit facilities, and time-saving (Chin, 2014; Garga & Bambale, 2016). To the company, repeat purchase can make an organization to achieve market share growth and increase its revenue in terms of profitability (Sharp & Sharp, 2008)

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Specification of Model Fig 2.1

In line with hypotheses of the study, model was developed conceptually to determine relationship between independent variables (packaging attributes) and dependent variable (Profitability) of bakery firms in Enugu State. The model specifies that profitability of small and medium bakery Firms is a function of design of wrapper and printed information of the product.

Theoretical Framework

Distinctive Competency Theory

Distinctive competence" was propounded by Philip Selznick's (1949). Michael and Ireland (1985) posited that the capability of an organization manifest in its demonstrated and potential ability to accomplish whatever it sets out to do. They observed that what a firm can do, to a large extent, is a function of the resources at the disposal of the company and not just the opportunities it confronts. They opined that the veritable tool to a company's success has to do with its ability to find and or create a competence that is truly unique. Distinctive competences are those peculiar things that a firm or its units can do better when compared to its competitors. Michael and Ireland (1985) a firm can develop distinctive capabilities in such areas as general administration, operations, finance, research and development, marketing, personnel, etc. It can be added that distinctive

competence can help a firm to be better positioned to create value that can enhance performance. Competencies represent major factors which can give rise to success in organizations (Levina & Ross, 2003). Distinctive competencies can be considered as uncommon abilities a company enjoys in an industry and which serves as a platform to create value for customers which in turn lead to competitive advantage. An SME that develops distinctive competence in packaging of its products will definitely enjoy patronage by customers and be profitable.

Empirical Review

Dhurup, Mafini and Dumasi (2023) also studied the impact of packaging, price and brand awareness on brand loyalty using evidence from the paint retailing industry. The result indicated that product packaging has a significant relationship with brand loyalty.

Shahram, et al (2023) studied the effect of packaging quality on performance of Saffron Export. The researchers focused on firms that export saffron in Khorason Razavi province. They employed questionnaire as the major instrument for data collection and used the SPSS software to perform a multiple regression analysis on the study variables. The result indicated that packaging quality has a significant effect on patronage of firms exporting saffron products in Khorasan Razavi Province.

Kiumarsi et al., (2024) also did a study titled Marketing Strategies to Improve the Sales of Bakery Products of Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Malaysia using survey research design methodology. Findings reveal that SMEs have unstructured marketing strategies and needs enhancements in the areas of packaging, value addition to the bakery products, focus on promotion and appropriate advertising strategies.

Adam and Ali (2024) investigated the impact of verbal elements of packaging of packaged milk on consumer buying behaviour in Karachi. The result showed a nexus between nutritional information, product information and country of origin and consumer buying behaviour. Methods use included questionnaire for collecting data, convenience sampling technique and Pearson correlation for analysis.

Olawepo and Ibojo (2015) worked on the relationship between packaging and consumer purchase intention: A case study of Nestle Nigeria product showed positive nexus between packaging and consumer purchase intention. Methods employed included primary and secondary data sources, structured questionnaire, random sampling technique and multiple regressions.

In addition, Hussain, Ali, Ibrahim, Noreen and Ahmad (2015) worked on impact of product packaging on consumer perception and purchase intention in Pakistan. It was revealed that packaging inspired consumer to have good perception and intention.

Farooq, Habib and Aslam (2015) worked on influence of product packaging on consumer purchase intentions in Punjab. Result showed that there is a positive association between the product packaging and customer purchase intention. Methods adopted included descriptive analysis, probability sampling technique and the use of questionnaire to gather information/

Oladele, Olowookere, Okolugbo and Adegbola (2015) investigated product packaging as a predictive factor of consumer patronage of toothpaste in Ado-Ekiti. The study showed positive nexus between visual elements of packaging like (quantity, quality and colour) and customer patronage. Methods employed included; questionnaire for data collection, purposive sampling technique and Pearson-correlation for analysis.

In Gomez, Consuegra and Molina (2015), the importance of packaging in purchase and usage behaviour of milk in Spain was investigated. The result showed that packaging technical, functional and information quality contributed in no small measure to customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, Gomez, et al., investigation was on satisfaction rather than patronage, the fact remains that since satisfaction is an antecedent of patronage, this makes their studies relevant to the present study. To achieve objectives, 7-point Likert scale questionnaire, convenience sampling and partial least squares were utilised.

Ghosh (2016) examined packaging impact on the purchasing behaviour of consumers in a study of Mother Dairy in India. Survey research design was used. The sample size of 150 respondents was randomly selected for the study. The data obtained were analyzed using chi-square and Pearson Product Moment Correlation tests. The findings of the study showed that the predictor variables like background image, wrapper design, packaging colour and packaging innovation have significant relationship with the dependent variable (consumer purchase behaviour).

Karedza (2017) examined the impact of packaging designs on consumer purchasing behaviour of FMCG in Zimbabwe. The survey research design was used for the study. The sample size of 49 respondents from the retail sector was selected using stratified and convenience sampling technique. Data obtained for the study were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis. The findings revealed that packaging elements have a significant relationship with consumer buying decision.

Gap in Reviewed Literature

Most foreign and local renowned researchers have written exhaustively on product packaging as a concept in marketing. Most of these researchers majored their research mainly on package attributes such as colour, design, materials, graphics etc.; without considering the comprehensive impact of packaging on profitability. Also, there is scarcity of empirical studies that investigate the relationship between product packaging and profitability in the bakery industry, particularly in Enugu State. As such this study closed the gap by analysing the influence of product packaging on profitability of small and medium scale bakery firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Survey research design was adopted because of the complex relationships that exist between variables. Population of this study were made up of 2,800 respondents from 138 registered bakery firms in the state according to association of master bakers Enugu State chapter. Sample size of the study was 350. Purposive sampling techniques were adopted for this study. Research instrument for this study was a structured questionnaire. A total of 350 copies of the questionnaire were distributed amongst owners/managers and staff of bakery firms in Enugu State. One (1) questionnaire was administered to a representative manager and staff of each bakery firm. Regression model was designed to ascertain the causes and effect between dependent variable and independent variables. The hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance with $p < 0.05$ indicating statistical significance. To enhance data analysis, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS, version 22.0) was used to analyze the data.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Correlation Analysis

Table 1. Inter-Correlation Between Variables

Variables		Profitability	Design wrapper	ofPrinted Information
Profitability	Pearson Correlation	-		
	Sig(2-tailed)			
	N			
Design of Wrapper	Pearson Correlation	.895**	-	
	Sig(2-tailed)	.000		
	N	322		
Printed Information	Pearson Correlation	.872**	.880**	-
	Sig(2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	322	322	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

As shown in the Table 4.3, design of wrapper and printed information have a positive relationship with profitability. Profitability shows extremely great relationship with the two independent variables which consist of design of wrapper (0.895) and printed information (0.872).

Regression Analysis

Table 2. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Error of the Estimate
1	0.925 ^a	0.855	0.853	0.37536

^a Predictors: (Constant), Design of Wrapper and Printed Information.

Table 4.4 revealed that 85.5% of the independent variables had a significant influence on profitability among bakery firms in Enugu State. Other factors account further remaining 14.5%. Multiple regression is used as a test of hypotheses and is used to determine whether independent factors can predict the dependent variable.

Table 3. Coefficients Analysis

Coefficients ^a				
Model		Beta	t-Ratio	Sig.t
1	Profitability (Constant)		5.165	0.000
	Design of Wrapper	0.339	6.098	0.000
	Printed Information	0.183	3.469	0.001

^a Dependent Variable: Profitability

The coefficients for each variable are shown in Table 4.5, shows that the independent variables design of wrapper ($\beta = 0.339$, $t = 6.098$, $p = 0.000$) and printed information ($\beta = 0.183$, $t = 3.469$, $p = 0.001$) are significantly related to the dependent variable profitability as the p-value of each variable is less than 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$)

Summary of Finding

- i. There is a positive and significant effect of design of wrappers on profitability of small and medium bakery firms in Enugu State.
- ii. There is a positive and significant influence of printed information on profitability of small and medium bakery firms in Enugu State.

Conclusion

The study focused on the influence of product packaging on profitability of small and medium enterprise (SME) in Enugu state, Nigeria. The results clearly showed that design of wrapper and printed information have significant positive relationship on profitability of bakery firms. The results also revealed that an improvement in package attributes acting as a value creating strategies has a positive influence on profitability of bakery firms. Therefore, it is concluded that packaging plays an important role that could influence significantly the marketability of SME's products in the market place.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. SME's should carefully choose colour combination that are capable of appealing to customers' interests and consequently influence their choice of a product by mere sighting of the package.
- ii. Innovative ideas in terms of major or minor modification in product packages should be given attention by bakery firms to attract consumers' patronage and enhance profitability.
- iii. Improvement on information on the product packages by bakery firms, especially nutrition align formation is recommended to attract consumers' patronage to their products and enhance profitability.

REFERENCES

- Adam, MandAli, K. (2024). Impact of packaging elements of packaged milk on consumer buying behaviour. Institute of Business Administration International Conference on Marketing, 3, 1-45.
- Agariya et al (2022). The role of packaging in brand communication. International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, 3(2), 1-13.
- Ahmadi, G., Bahrami, H., and Ahani, M. (2018). An investigation of visual components of packaging on food consumer behaviour. Business and Economic Research, 3(2), 1-11.

- Ahmed, R., Parmar, V. and Amin, M. (2017). Impact of product packaging on consumers buying behaviour. *European Journal of Scientific Research*,120 (2),145-157.
- Bear, J. (2023). Sustaining labeling schemes: The topic of their claims and function. *Journal of Business Strategy and Environment*,12(4),254-264.
- Belch, G., Belch, M. and Purani, K. (2021). Advertising and promotion: An integrated marketingcommunicationperspective.7thEdition.McGraw-HillCompaniesInc.,New York.
- Borishade et al (2022). Empirical study of packaging and its effect on consumer purchase decision in a food and beverages firm. *European Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(11), 44-53
- Deliya, M. and Parmar, B. (2019). Role of packaging on consumer buying behavior Patan District. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*,12(10),49-67.
- Dunmade,E.(2021).Packagingandconsumer’spurchasedecision:AstudyofUnilever’sproducts.*International Journal of Social Sciences*,2(4),1-17.
- Farooq,S.,Habib,S.,andAslam,S.(2015).Influenceofproductpackagingonconsumerpurchaseintentions.*International Journal of Economic, Commerce and Management*. 3(12),538-547.
- Ghosh,B.(2016).ImpactofPackagingonconsumers’buyingbehaviour:AcaseofMotherdairy,Kolkata.*Journal of Management*,12(1),63-69.
- Gofman,A.,Moskowitz,H.andMets,T.(2018).Acceleratingstructuredconsumer-drivenpackagingdesign.*Journal of Consumer Marketing*,27(2), 157-168
- Grundey, D, (2019). Functionality of product packaging: Surveying Consumers attitude towards selected cosmetic brands. *Journal of EconomicandSociology*,3(1), 87-103.
- Harper,M.andMiller,B.(2018).Makingafragranceconnectionthroughcolour.*Global CosmeticsIndustry*, 180(1),28-29.
- Hoyer, W. and MacInnis, D. (2018). *Consumer behaviour*. 5th Edition. Cengage Learning, South Western – USA<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/design>(Retrievedon30thMarch2020)
- Hutchinson, R. (2018). *Discovering shifts and trends in beverage packaging*. California: College of Liberal Art Polytechnic State University, San Luis, Obispo, 1-25

Karedza, G. (2017). The Impact of Packaging design on consumer buying behaviour of FMCG during the Hyper-inflationary and after the Dollarisation era in Harare, Zimbabwe. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(1), 20-30.

Kotler, P. (2016). *Marketing management*. 13th Edition. Prentice Hall, New Jersey

Kotler, P. and Keller, K. (2016). *Marketing management*. 14th Edition. Pearson Education Inc., New Jersey, 368.

Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (2016). *Principles of marketing*. 16th Edition. Pearson Education, New York.

Lynsey, L. (2017). Thinking outside the carton: Attitudes towards milk packaging. *British Food Journal*, 115(6), 899-912. NPC (National Population Commission) (2015). *Projected Population Report*.

Nwulu, C. and Asiegbu, K. (2015). Advancement inclination behaviours and University staff patronage of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 2(6), 94-104.

Poturak, M. (2019). Influence of product packaging on purchase decisions. *European Journal of Social and Human Sciences*, 3(3), 144-150. Pride, W. and Farrel, O. (2010). *Marketing South-Western* Cengage Learning, Mason (USA)

Rundh, B. (2018). Linking packaging to marketing: How packaging influencing marketing strategy. *British Food Journal*, 115(11), 1547-1563.

Shah, S. Ahmad, A. and Ahmad, N. (2013). Role of packaging in consumer buying behaviour: A study of university students of Peshawar KPK Pakistan. *International Journal of Review of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 1 (2): 35-41

Silayoi, P. and Speece M. (2017). The importance of packaging attributes: A conjoint analysis approach. *European Journal of Marketing*, 41 (11/12), 1495-1517).

Silayoi, P. and Speece, M. (2018). Packaging and purchase decisions. An exploratory study on the impact of involvement level and time pressure. *British Food Journal*, 106 (8), 607-628.

Smith, P. and Taylor, J. (2021). *Marketing communication as an integrated approach*. 3th Edition. Kogan Page, London.

SPSS version 22. (2022). IBM Corp. Released 2011. *IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows*, Version

20.0.Armonk,NY:IBMCorp.

Tobias,P.(2018). Lifeisnotalwaysright:Placementofpictorialandtextualpackagingelements.
British Food Journal, 115(8),1211-1225.

White,S.(2019).Influenceofpackagingonconsumerbuyingbehaviour.1-10.<http://www.labelvalue.com>(Retrieved
on 25th April 2020)

Zekiri, J.and Hasani, V. (2019). The role and impact of the packaging effect on consumer buying behaviour.
EconomicForumReview,4(1),22